

RECENT RESEARCHES IN THE FIELD OF HORMONES AND THEIR APPLICATION TO THE MANUFACTURE OF GLANDULAR PRODUCTS IN INDIA*

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Nowhere in the whole domain of pure chemical science has intensive research, carried out during the past few decades, led to more fruitful and astonishing results than in the field of hormones. Abel¹ gave us crystalline adrenaline from the adrenal glands of oxen in 1901, and Kendall² isolated crystalline thyroxine from the thyroid glands of cattle in 1914. In 1921 Banting and Best³ isolated from the pancreatic glands of dogs and foetal calves potent extracts of insulin which in combination with zinc can now be had in the form of pure crystals. Since 1920 rapid strides have been made in our knowledge of the chemistry of the pituitary gland⁴; oxytocin and vasopressin have been successfully fractionated and are now available in concentrated and almost pure forms and some of the anterior pituitary hormones are also claimed to have been isolated in the crystalline form. The years 1930 to 1943⁵ witnessed the isolation of an array of crystalline steroid hormones—the androgens, the oestrogens, the progestational hormones and the cortical hormones. Liver extracts⁶ are now available in extremely concentrated forms, one c.c. of which administered parenterally keeps the anaemic patient fit for weeks together. These great achievements have been made possible only by the successful and harmonious co-operation between the chemists on the one hand and the clinicians on the other.

I propose in the course of this lecture to dwell briefly on the salient features of the developments in this field, considering them as far as possible in the sequence in which they have been taking place.

ADRENAL GLANDS

Taking first the adrenal gland hormones for consideration, we find that there are two of these glands situated like pear-shaped caps above the two kidneys.

The whole gland consists of two parts, the medulla and the cortex, the adrenaline being concentrated entirely in the medulla. The morphological characters of these glands obtained from some of the South Indian animals are shown in Fig. 1.

It will be noted that while the adrenal glands of sheep are of a uniform oblong structure, those of the cattle are uneven in contour showing deep clefts in many cases. Again the left adrenal differs in appearance from the right and the adrenals of the ox often show a marked difference in shape from those of the buffalo. The following table (Table I) gives the average weight of the adrenal glands, the percentage content of the medullary tissue and the adrenaline content (mg. per gram of whole tissue) of the animals from the Madras slaughter house.

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TABLE I

Adrenaline contents of glands.

	Average wt. of gland in g.	Percentage of medullary tissue.	Adrenaline content (mg./g.)
Cattle	8—10	25—29	1.85
Sheep	1.5—2.5	17—20	1.57
Pig	2—4	17—20	0.8

That extracts of adrenal glands possessed the property of raising the blood pressure was the first startling discovery made as early as 1894 by Oliver and Schafer⁷ which aroused the great interest of chemists and stimulated research in gland products in general. Fundamental work on the preparation of the active principle was carried out in Abel's laboratory in Baltimore although the actual isolation was achieved in the research laboratories of Park Davis & Co. in 1901 by Aldrich⁸ who had previously been an assistant in Abel's laboratory and by Takamine independently of each other. The elucidation of its constitution by analytical means was soon followed by synthesis, Dakin's process⁹ starting from catechol being now actually employed by several commercial firms.

Fig 1
Adrenal gland.

The natural process of preparation from glands is commonly based on the solubility of the base in acidified solvents like alcohol, the free base being thrown down from these

extracts by the cautious addition of ammonia. Being crystalline, the substance can be readily purified and the purity checked by melting point and optical rotation, and also by colorimetric assays and ultimately confirmed, when necessary, by bio-assay.

Our annual requirements of adrenaline in normal times have been estimated to be of the order of 10 kgs. of the free base. From Table V it will be evident that in normal times of peace the slaughter houses of ten of our major cities, Bombay, Calcutta, Delhi, Madras, Hyderabad, Lahore, Karachi, Lucknow, Dacca and Bangalore, handle annually about 320,100 cattle which will yield about 3,201,000 g. of adrenal tissue and about 3,071,500 sheep which in its turn will yield about 6,143,000 g. of adrenal tissue. From this total of approximately ten thousand kilograms of adrenal tissue, a net amount of over 10 kg. of pure adrenaline can easily be isolated. It seems, therefore, that India ought to be self-sufficient as regards at least her own needs of this most valuable drug.

Although closely related compounds possessing the sympathomimetic action of adrenaline have been prepared either synthetically or from natural sources, the most important of these being ephedrine, none of them have been able to replace adrenaline which is one of the essential and most powerful drugs of the present day.

THE CORTEX

The adrenal cortex, unlike the medulla, is considered to be essential for life as it controls the vital metabolisms of carbohydrate, salt and water. No single substance which can be described as the vital hormone of the cortex is elaborated by the gland but a surprisingly large number of closely related compounds having specified effects, qualitatively different one from the other, have been prepared from it. The intensive researches carried out during the last seven years (1935—1942) by three different groups of workers—Kendall (America), Wintersteiner (America) and Reichstein (Switzerland⁵) have resulted in the isolation of a series of crystalline compounds from the adrenal cortex, typical examples of which are corticosterone, dehydrocorticosterone and desoxycorticosterone. Their constitutions have been established beyond doubt and one of these, desoxycorticosterone, is now synthesised and made available for clinical use. For medical purposes, however, a whole extract of the cortex containing all the hormones in a fairly pure and concentrated form and known popularly as Cortin is preferred.

Statistics are not available regarding the requirements of cortical extracts in India, but there is no doubt that enough extract can be manufactured for supplying all our needs. The methods of extraction are rather complicated, involving as they do initial extraction with lipoidal solvents, scrupulous removal of the last traces of adrenaline and final purification by fractional distribution between different organic solvents.

THE THYROID GLAND

The thyroid gland consists of two lobes, situated on either side of the wind-pipe connected usually by a narrow isthmus. The morphological characters of those of some of the South Indian animals are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2
Thyroid gland.

It will be noted that the thyroid glands in the case of both cattle and sheep possess a long and narrow isthmus, whereas in the case of the pig, the two lobes are fused together lengthwise. The description given in literature that the shape of the thyroid glands resembles that of a purse with the flaps opened up seems to apply, therefore, only to the pig thyroids.

Thyroid is most commonly and probably, best, administered as the desiccated whole gland. The fresh glands are cleaned free from fat and connective tissues, dried at a temperature not exceeding 60°, defatted with a solvent like petroleum ether and diluted with lactose so that the final product has a thyroxine-iodine content of 0.1%. Thyroxine itself is, however, indicated in acute cases of thyroid deficiency and also in those few cases where oral doses of the desiccated gland are not tolerated. The isolation of thyroxine is by no means easy, involving as it does hydrolysis with graded strengths of baryta and final purification through the sodium salt. Thyroxine itself is insoluble and is, therefore, always administered parenterally as the sodium salt.

It was discovered in the course of these investigations that thyroid glands of local animals contained a higher proportion of total iodine and thyroxine-iodine than those reported of animals in Europe, and this observation has been independently confirmed from the Biochemical Standardisation Laboratory, Calcutta^{1a}.

The following table (Table II) represents the total iodine and thyroxine-iodine contents as well as the absolute weights of the glands of cattle, sheep and pigs, obtained from the Madras slaughter house.

TABLE II

Iodine content of desiccated thyroid gland.

	Average weight of glands.	Total iodine.	Thyroxine iodine.
Cattle	9—10g.	0·91%	0·35%
Sheep	1·5—2	0·66	0·26
Pig	3—6	0·84	0·39

These values may be compared with the figure 0·235% for the thyroxine-iodine of a standard specimen of desiccated thyroid obtained from the British Drug House in London.

The efficacy of the whole gland for the correction of myxoedema was established as early as 1891 by Murray, but the supposed active principle, thyroxine, was isolated by Kendall² in pure crystalline condition only at the end of 1914. Nearly a decade later Harington¹¹ interested himself in the subject and soon worked out a method for the isolation of the hormone in very much better yields. He also established its correct structure and in collaboration with Barger, ultimately succeeded in synthesising the hormone—a synthesis which is now being adopted by some of the commercial firms in Europe. The satisfaction of the chemist in having isolated the real hormone of the gland was, however, rather short-lived, as it was soon found that the whole thyroid gland was more active than pure thyroxine on an equi-iodine content basis. The consensus of opinion at the present day is that the real hormone of the thyroid gland is either thyreoglobulin itself or an intrinsic part thereof, most probably a complex peptide made up of the following components in its structure. (Thyroxine radical—Amino acid radicals—Diiodotyrosin radical).

The assay of thyroid extracts is best carried out chemically by estimating the total organic iodine, the modern view being that the physiological potency of thyroid is dependent more on the total organic iodine than on the thyroxine-iodine. The chemical assay can always be checked, if necessary, by one of the several biological methods, the most accurate being that based on basal metabolism.

Fortunately enough, thyroid deficiency diseases are rare in India and enough thyroid is available, say from the Madras slaughter houses alone, to treat perhaps all the cases of thyroid deficiency occurring throughout India.

Attempts have been made to iodinate proteins in order to obtain synthetic iodo compounds, which would simulate the natural thyreoglobulin in physiological activity. Success was finally achieved in 1939 by two German chemists, Ludwig and Mutzenbecher¹⁴, who iodinated casein under carefully controlled conditions and obtained a product which showed thyroid activity. This product and the concentrates obtained by its hydrolysis have been prepared in this laboratory and are being put to trial in some of the clinics in Madras. Ludwig and Mutzenbecher succeeded in isolating crystalline thyroxine itself by hydrolysis of this portein—a remarkable discovery which has been confirmed now by

Harington¹⁵. The synthesis of thyroxine *in vivo* from the diiodotyrosine molecule has also been experimentally established very recently¹⁶.

The fate of iodine in the body, its absorption by the thyroid gland and the subsequent changes are now being investigated in American laboratories by a novel technique, namely, by the use of radioactive (labelled) iodine¹⁷. These researches hold out promise of important developments not only in the field of pure chemistry, but also in its clinical applications.

THE PARATHYROID GLANDS

The parathyroid glands, which are the smallest of the ductless glands, consist of two pairs of glands, one pair lying on each side of the neck, close to the thyroid or embedded in it.

No pure chemical individual has yet been isolated from the parathyroid. "Parathormone", which contains the active principle (of a protein type) in a rather crude form, is usually obtained by Collip's method⁹, where the fresh glands are minced and extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid at 100°, the mixture is cooled and the solidified fat, etc, removed by filtration. Inert protein is now removed by precipitation by adjusting the pH to 5.5.

The filtrate containing the active principles is adjusted to Congo-red pH and saturated with NaCl, when parathormone is obtained in a solid form. This is dissolved in very dilute hydrochloric acid and sterilised by passing through Berkfeld filter and administered by the intravenous or the subcutaneous route. The active principle is isolated sometimes also as the picrate, as in the case of insulin.

The parathyroids are concerned with the regulation of the calcium metabolism and the controlling of the concentration of calcium and phosphorus in the blood serum. Deficiency of the secretion leads to acute symptoms of tetany, which is characterised by a decrease in the serum calcium.

Cases of parathyroid deficiency do not appear to be very common in India, and it is certain that enough extracts for our needs can certainly be prepared by mobilising the glands of some of our slaughtereries.

Substitution therapy with parathyroid extracts has now been largely replaced by treatment with irradiated sterol derivatives, the most important of which is dihydrocholesterol known popularly as A. T. 10.

THE PANCREAS

The importance of the discovery of insulin and its application as a drug can hardly be overestimated. The history of the investigations of Banting and Best on the hormones of the pancreas in Professor MacLeod's laboratory in the University of Toronto, the preparation of potent extracts having powerful hypoglycemic action from the pancreas of foetal calves in 1921, and the taking out of patents for the manufacture of insulin by the Insulin Committee appointed by the Toronto University in 1923 are now generally well known.

Insulin is now prepared from fresh pancreas by processes involving preliminary extraction with acidified solvents, removal of protein impurities by precipitation with graded strengths of alcohol, followed by isoelectric precipitation or purification through the picrate. The final product after bio-assay is sterilised by filtration.

The maximum concentration of insulin is found in foetal calves and diminishes progressively with the age of the cattle. This is illustrated in the following table (Table III) containing yields of insulin in international units per g. of tissue from the pancreas of cattle of different ages.

TABLE III

Foetal calves up to 5 months	...	...	33 I. U.
Foetal calves between 5 and 7 months	...	...	23
Calves from 6 to 8 weeks	...	...	11.5
Cows 2 years old	...	...	5
Fully grown animals	...	...	2

Certain classes of fish known as the Teleostoi, the cod being a typical example, in which the islet tissue exists separate from the main pancreatic gland, yield 15 to 30 units of insulin per gram of tissue which is nearly 10 times the yield obtained from the pancreas of domestic animals. The suggestion that the islets of fish might furnish a convenient practical source of insulin was first made by MacLeod and this aspect of the subject was investigated by McCormick and Noble in America and by Dudley in England in connexion with the fisheries of these two countries¹⁹.

It is doubtful if locally made insulin has ever been put on the Indian market. Researches on its preparation are being pursued in the laboratories of the Indian Institute of Science, and there is every reason to hope that these researches will lead to the production of insulin on a sufficiently large scale for our requirements. The possibility of utilising the raw material of our fisheries for the production of insulin and also of protamine also needs careful investigation.

Attempts made to prolong the action of insulin in subcutaneous doses so as to avoid giving frequent injections led to the introduction of Protamine-Insulin by Hagedorn²⁰ in 1935 and its modification by Scott²¹ into Protamine-Zinc-Insulin in the following year. These together constitute perhaps the greatest advance in the treatment of diabetes mellitus since the discovery of insulin itself. Hagedorn and his co-workers in Copenhagen carried out a series of experiments on the solubility of insulin combined with different protamines and succeeded in producing a protamine-insulin suspension which when injected subcutaneously is absorbed considerably more slowly than soluble insulin hydrochloride and thus exerts a more prolonged hypoglycoemic action. This substance termed protamine-insulin was improved upon still further by Scott and Fisher who on the results of experiments on the zinc contents of insulin preparations tried the effect of adding small quantities of zinc salts to protamine-insulin. As a result of these researches, the new compound Zinc-Protamine-Insulin has been introduced into practice. The standard consists of a batch of zinc-insulin crystals, one milligram of which contains by international agreement 22 units of insulin.

THE PITUITARY GLAND

The pituitary gland, situated in a cavity "Sella turcica" at the base of the brain, produces a battery of hormones and has been described, perhaps aptly, as the leader of the endocrine orchestra. The following photographs (Fig. 3) illustrate the morphological characters of the pituitary glands of cattle, sheep and pigs obtained from the Madras slaughter house.

Fig. 3
Pituitary gland

The pituitary is made up of two parts termed the anterior and the posterior lobes which elaborate entirely different principles. The following table (Table IV) gives the average weight of the pituitary gland, and the ratio of the anterior to the posterior lobe, in the case of the glands of animals obtained from the local slaughter house¹⁰.

TABLE IV

	Average weight.	$\frac{\text{Anterior lobe}}{\text{posterior lobe}}$
Cattle	0.8—1.5 g.	2.3—2.8
Sheep	0.3—0.4 g.	8—11
Pig	0.2 g.	1.2—1.5

It will be apparent from the table that sheep are comparatively poor sources for the posterior lobe. They are, however, ideal for the isolation and studies of the anterior lobe principles. Figures available in literature go to show that ox-pituitaries of European animals weigh on the average 2.5 grams, the posterior lobe weighing only 0.5 g. It will thus be seen that while the pituitary glands of local cattle weigh less, the ratio of the posterior to anterior lobe is definitely higher.

Pituitrin, one of the indispensable drugs of the present day, is isolated from the posterior lobe. The method is simple, involving the extraction of the dissected posterior lobes or the desiccated posterior powder with 0.25% acetic acid the concentration being so adjusted that each c.c. of the fluid extract contains 10 international units. In 1928 Kamm¹¹ fractionated pituitrin into (a) oxytocin which stimulates the uterus, and (b) vasopressin which raises the blood pressure, but more recent investigations tend to show that the posterior pituitary elaborates one single hormone which gets split up into various fractions during the processing. In 1942 Van Dyke and his colleagues¹² isolated a protein from the

posterior lobes of frozen ox pituitaries which they claim is pure and which contains all the active fractions.

The annual requirements in India of posterior pituitary extracts correspond at present to about 2,500 grams of the dried posterior powder. This amount can certainly be produced by tapping the resources of only a few of our larger slaughter houses.

Dried posterior pituitary powder, prepared in this laboratory, has been found on bio-assay to correspond with the international standard.

THE ANTERIOR PITUITARY LOBES

The anterior pituitary can be processed to give a number of hormones, all of which are supposed to be of protein nature and some of which are claimed to have been prepared in the crystalline condition³⁴. The more important of these are the lactogenic, the gonadotropic and the thyrotropic principles. The least encouraging situation to-day is the clinical application of the experimental findings in the field of anterior pituitary hormones. Although those findings have certainly improved our diagnosis of pituitary disorders in man, they have added little to their control. It may at least be said that we have not scored a success in pituitary therapy comparable to that of the thyroid, pancreas and adrenal glands.

THE SEX HORMONES

The production of definite endocrine secretions by the sex glands had been guessed for a long time, spayed and castrated animals showing atrophy of the sex characteristics if they were mature, or failing to develop the secondary sexual characteristics if they were immature. The actual isolation of the various hormones was, however, delayed for a long time, principally on account of the extremely low concentration in which these principles were found in the actual glands. Between the years 1925 and 1930 a number of happy discoveries was made such as that of pregnancy urine as an exceptionally rich source of the oestrogenic hormones, the elaboration of the vaginal smear test for the oestrogens and the capon comb test for the androgens, etc., which made possible the successful isolation in crystalline form of the various oestrogenic, androgenic and progestational hormones³⁵. Typical examples of these are oestrone, oestradiol, testosterone and progesterone. For clinical use oestradiol is obtained from pregnancy urine. Oestrone is manufactured from the urine of pregnant mares, testosterone from testicular tissue and also synthetically from cholesterol and progesterone only synthetically from stigmasterol, since the supply of *Corpora lutea* is strictly limited.

Even after the pure hormones were isolated, the clinician was confronted with many new problems. The hormones were rapidly absorbed by the blood stream and were often excreted as such in the urine or detoxicated by the liver, even when administered parenterally. In the hope of finding some product whose action would be slow, steady and prolonged and thus simulate the function of the natural healthy glands, various esters of the hormones were prepared some of which have been successful and now introduced into practice. Oestradiol is now administered as the benzoate and testosterone as the propionate or the methyl ester. The latest innovation in the field of sex hormone therapy consists in the actual implantation of tablets by making incisions in the skin of the

hypogastric region and embedding sterilised tablets of the hormones inside and suturing up the skin with cat-gut ; these pellets have been claimed to be active for months.

Although the sex hormones are now finding use in the treatment of various sex disorders both in man and in woman, and also for the correction of hypogonadism²⁶, their use in clinical practice may be considered to be still in the experimental stage. Several synthetic substances like hexestrol and stilbestrol have also come into the market, and some of these are claimed to be effective even on oral administration. The greatest caution has, however, to be exercised in the use of these synthetic substitutes as reports of untoward symptoms or of their acting even as cumulative poisons are not uncommon.

LIVER AND STOMACH EXTRACTS

The efficacy of liver for the cure of pernicious anaemia was discovered by Minot and Murphy²⁷ in 1926. About eighteen years have lapsed since that time and we are still in the dark as regards the chemical nature of the active principle or principles. For working in this field the chemist has to face very heavy odds since the only satisfactory method of assay is the clinical test on pernicious anaemic patients, animal experiments having proved far from satisfactory. It can be claimed, however, that liver extracts are now available in highly purified forms, the amount of material needed by the patient per day being decreased from 400 g. to less than 10 mg.

Dr. Cohn²⁸ of the Harvard Medical School was the first to isolate in 1927 an active fraction (Fraction G) from whole liver by methods involving the removal of the gross impurities by heat coagulation and treatment with alcohol. An amorphous powder was obtained which had the properties of nitrogenous base. Dakin and associates^{29, 30} took the concentration a step further by using Reinecke salt to effect the precipitation of the active fraction. Hydrolysis of the product yielded a series of amino-acids and Dakin came to the conclusion that the haemopoietic principle of the liver is, or is associated with, a peptide possessing many of the properties of an albumose.

During the years 1936-42 several groups of workers³¹ have been working on the subject, namely, Subbarow and Jacobson in Boston, Laland and Klem in Strendell's laboratory in Oslo, and Paul Karrer in Zurich. The active principle was quantitatively adsorbed by charcoal and eluted by means of phenol. These researches go to show that the active principle is of a multiple nature ; continued fractionation of liver extracts resulting in partial or complete extinction of therapeutic activity which was recovered by admixture of the purified materials with the other fractions. These fractions have been termed accessory factors, for while like co-enzymes they are by themselves therapeutically inert, they augment the activity of the primary factor or factors contained in the purified fractions. Up to now four such accessory factors, isolated from crude liver preparations, have been identified, *viz*, (1) *l*-tyrosine in a yield of 6 mg., (2) a complex purine of the pterine class, (3) a peptide in a yield of 14 mg. and (4) tryptophane in yields of 5 mg. each per 100 g. of whole liver. The primary factor itself is considered to be a complex pyridine compound.

The fact that pernicious anæmia is associated with diseases of the stomach has been known for some time. In 1929 Castle³² showed that meat which had been digested with stomach would cure pernicious anæmia although raw meat would not. He postulated the

presence in gastric juice of an enzyme 'Haemopoietin' or the "intrinsic" factor which reacted with an "extrinsic" factor in the meat with the formation of the P. A. factor, which is then absorbed and stored in the liver, probably after suitable modification. Recent researches have largely confirmed Castle's hypothesis; there is an antianaemic "liver principle" and an antianaemic "stomach principle" and both are capable of relieving pernicious anaemia. These two antianaemic principles, *Anahaemin* and *Haemopoietin* as they have been called, although quite distinct are closely related in certain respects. The liver principle is a thermostable substance, relatively stable to many reagents and solvents and moderately resistant to digestion with trypsin, pepsin and erepsin. Haemopoietin, on the other hand, is a thermolabile enzyme, distinct from pepsin and rennin and always associated with protein; it is relatively unstable and very easily destroyed by chemical reagents and many solvents and by enzymes such as pepsin and trypsin and by heating to 60°.

Pernicious anaemia is due primarily to the deficiency of the intrinsic factor and so the treatment consists in either supplying the intrinsic factor in the form of stomach preparations whereby the elaboration of the haemopoietic principle by the stomach is stimulated or by the actual administration of the pre-formed active principle in the form of liver extracts.

Liver and stomach extracts are widely used in India for the treatment of anaemia and a variety of other diseases. Liver extracts which are available for either parenteral or oral use, are processed by extraction of fresh liver with alcoholic solutions, followed by precipitation and removal of the protein impurities. The preparation of stomach extracts involves the desiccation of the lining of the stomach at a sufficiently low temperature. Potent extracts of liver and stomach have now been placed on the market by several commercial firms in India, but very few of them are believed to be as successful as the German and American preparations.

From the brief review given in the preceding pages, it will be clear that gland products like adrenaline, insulin, pituitrin, liver extracts, etc., have become indispensable for the welfare of any community in the modern age, and added importance has to be attached at the present moment to some of these drugs, as they have become of urgent importance in connexion with the war. It was, therefore, in the fitness of things, that a comprehensive scheme of research into the preparation of gland products in India was subsidized by the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research early in 1941.

THE CATTLE WEALTH OF INDIA

The cattle population of India is considered to be one of the largest; India being supposed to possess almost a third of the world's cattle. The raw material for the production of gland products may, therefore, be drawn in large quantities from our slaughter houses where the domesticated animals are killed daily for human consumption. The following table, (Table V) represents the average peace-time statistics of the animals slaughtered every year in some of the more important cities in India.

TABLE V

Number of animals slaughtered per year.

	Buffaloes, bullocks, cows and calves.	Sheep and goats.		Buffaloes, bullocks, cows and calves.	Sheep and goats.
Bombay	84,800	799,000	Lahore	17,900	247,000
Calcutta	83,000	230,000	Karachi	16,400	195,000
Delhi	54,000	384,000	Lucknow	10,000	149,000
Madras	1,9000	468,000	Dacca	16,500	47,600
Hyderabad	18,200	498,300	Bangalore	--	53,600

These are only approximate figures and the numbers must now have considerably increased due to the present military situation and the necessity for exporting dehydrated meat to foreign countries. The table reveals the important fact that a large and steady supply of raw material is available in India even in normal times of peace for the large scale production of glandular products and that a central factory for their manufacture might profitably be started in one of the major cities like Bombay, Calcutta, Delhi or Madras.

THE ORGANIZATION OF THE SLAUGHTER HOUSES.

The organizations which have been perfected in the abattoirs of Europe and in the packing houses of America, are, however, completely absent in the slaughteries in India. Although several thousands of animals are killed daily in our cities, there are hardly any facilities existing at present for the collection and preservation of the glands, so that they might be worked up later or sent to a distant place where the factory for the production of glandular products would be situated. Insulated chambers, cooled by refrigerating machinery, are the essential features of all modern abattoirs. Immediately after the animals are killed, the dressed carcasses are removed to the cold room, where they are kept for several hours during which time all the endocrine glands are skilfully removed under expert supervision. These are, then, frozen and conveyed in iced and insulated trucks to local firms, if there are any, or packed into large refrigerated chambers in ships, which take them to distant countries across the seas. In our country, on the other hand, there are hardly any slaughteries which can boast of insulated cold rooms with the result that there is little time available for the selection and removal of the glands which in several cases have their potent principles destroyed to a large extent even by one hour's delay of removal, on account of the setting in of autolysis.

To give one illustration, we may consider the case of the pituitary gland. To dissect this out, the skull has to be opened and the brain exposed, a process during which the matter of the brain undergoes rapid deterioration at the ordinary temperature, and is thereby rendered unfit for human consumption afterwards. If, on the other hand, our slaughteries had been furnished with suitable refrigeratory systems, these brains, after the removal of the pituitary, could easily have been kept frozen without the slightest change or loss of freshness until demanded by the public. From the fact that in some of the coastal parts of India, fish is being successfully refrigerated and supplied in a fresh condition to the interior parts, it will be evident that the introduction of refrigerated chambers in our slaughter houses should permit a similar transport not only of glands for commercial purposes, but also of meat for domestic consumption, in perfect condition of freshness and flavour from the larger cities to the interior parts.

PRESERVATION AND STORAGE OF GLANDS

The major slaughtereries in India are widely scattered and for the processing of glands in a central factory, we have to study the best conditions for the storage. The tropical heat prevailing in our country militates against the possibility of keeping the dissected glands for any length of time at the ordinary temperatures. Again, the different glands vary as regards the stability and susceptibility to change of the particular hormones concerned. In the case of these glands whose hormones are specially sensitive, e. g. in the case of insulin, the extraction must be commenced immediately. In the case of certain other glands like the adrenal and the parathyroids, the glands can be frozen immediately after dissection and transported in this condition to the laboratory or factory.

Investigations carried out in these laboratories^{3,4} have shown that frozen adrenal glands preserve for several days and that even after a fortnight's storage in the frozen condition the loss in adrenaline content is not serious. The actual data are given in the following table (Table VI).

TABLE VI

Changes in adrenaline content when the glands are kept frozen.

Period of storage.	Adrenaline content (mg/g. of gland persulphate colour reaction).
Fresh glands	1.85
Frozen glands stored for one day	1.72
Frozen glands stored for 1 week	1.58
Frozen glands stored for 2 weeks	1.51

Similarly freezing appears also to preserve the potency of pituitary glands^{3,4}. In the following table (Table VII) are given values for the vitamin-C contents of the pituitary glands which have been stored for varying periods in the frozen state. The loss in the vitamin content is not very appreciable even after two weeks' storage and it is possible that physiological potency, too, is affected only to a similarly slight extent.

TABLE VII

Change in vitamin-C content in frozen pituitary glands.

Period of storage	Vitamin-C content (mg/g. of fresh gland).
Fresh glands	1.30
Glands kept frozen for 1 day	1.28
Glands kept frozen for 1 week	1.16
Glands kept frozen for 2 weeks	1.16

In the case of the posterior pituitary, the active principles are not soluble in organic solvents, so that the tissue can be conveniently dried by treatment with successive batches of acetone and in the final dried condition the powder can be stored for several months, especially when kept at a low temperature and out of contact with air.

In the case of the thyroid gland, the active principle is stable towards heat and is insoluble in lipoidal solvents, so that the glands can be successfully desiccated, *i. e.*, dried at fairly high temperature and then defatted and preserved until ready for subsequent processing.

It has been definitely proved from our experiments³⁴ that the active principles of the thyroid gland possess a remarkable stability. Figures which are reproduced in the following table (Table VIII) show that the value for thyroxine-iodine and for organic-iodine percentages are fairly constant irrespective of whether the glands have been chilled in dry ice immediately after the animals were slaughtered, or stored frozen for one month, or even whether the desiccated glands have been stored at the ordinary temperature (30°) for two years.

TABLE VIII

Condition.	Thyroxine-iodine (% total iodine).	Organic-iodine (% total iodine).
Cattle glands brought to the laboratory chilled in dry ice and desiccated immediately ...	39.86	98.33
Cattle glands frozen for one month ...	40.14	97.93
Desiccated cattle glands stored at 30° for 2 years	39.86	93.20

THE MAKING OF A DRUG.

The glandular principles have, in several instances, to be administered parenterally, and moreover, as they are potent in minute doses—sometimes even in fractions of a m g.—the greatest care has to be exercised in the control of dosage of the drugs. In the case of adrenaline and thyroxine, the products can be obtained in a pure crystalline condition and the final solutions can be made with accurately weighed quantities of the solids. Not so, however, is the case of certain other principles like insulin, liver extracts and pituitrin, for the assay of which suitable chemical, physical or physicochemical methods are not available. In these cases the finished products have to be biologically assayed and then properly dosed. Even when chemical methods are available for the assay of a hormone (e. g. the colorimetric method for the estimation of adrenaline), the final check must always be made with a biological method. A biological standardization department is, therefore, an essential pre-requisite of an up-to-date factory for the manufacture of glandular products. The importance of biological standardization of drugs has been critically reviewed by Dr. B. Mukerji³⁵ of the Biological Standardization Laboratory, Calcutta, in a recent editorial article in the columns of 'Current Science'!

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

No serious attempt has yet been made to tap the vast wealth of the slaughter houses in India. The raw material available in these places, if properly utilized, should not only supply all our requirements of such essential drugs as adrenaline, pituitrin, etc., but would also yield a variety of useful articles, such as meat extracts, gelatin, pepsin, trypsin, rennet, etc., not to mention the commoner products such as glue, manure, etc.

On account of the stress of the present abnormal circumstances due to the war, isolated efforts are no doubt being made by several laboratories and firms in India to

manufacture some of these gland products. It is doubtful, however, if the industry would be able to survive the serious post-war competition of the drug houses of Europe and America which is inevitable, unless our slaughteries are thoroughly overhauled and organized in the meantime with such safeguards of state control as may be essential and an exhaustive study of problems of storage and transport of the glands in Indian climatic conditions made, so that it becomes practicable to establish either a large central factory in India or several provincial factories, e.g. in Calcutta, Bombay, Madras and Delhi, where the glands from the numerous slaughteries could be collectively or individually processed.

A word may be added in conclusion regarding the suitability of manufacturing hormones synthetically in India. Considering the fact that our heavy chemical industry is still in its infancy and that there has been hardly any development yet in the manufacture of fine chemicals worth mentioning, it seems obvious that it would not be possible for many years to come to synthesise such complex drugs as hormones without importing many of the intermediate fine chemicals required for the purpose. We are, on the other hand, more favourably situated than most other countries in respect of our unbounded natural resources awaiting utilization, and the prospects, therefore, of starting the industry in this country from animal glands would appear to be definitely brighter.

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ADDENDA

Page.	Para.	Line.	for	Read
1	2	3	"...taking place"	"...taking place, and on their possibilities in India."
3	4	1	"extracts"	"hormones"
3	"	2	omit "extracts"	
3	4	3	"extraction"	"isolation"
3	5	1	"situated"	"situated at the neck"
4	1	4	...	Read "approximately" after "therefore"
5	3	13,14	...	"Structure: Thyroxine: Amino-acid radicals: Di-iodotyrosin"
6	1	3	"radio-active (labelled)"	"radio-active or labelled"
6	2	3	...	"actually embedded in it (see Fig. 2, sheep thyroid)".
6	6	2	omit "certainly"	
7	3	1	"Teleostoi"	"Teleostei"
8	1	2	...	Read "...has been aptly described as the leader...."
9		1		"...they claim to be pure and to contain all the..."
9	2	2	...	insert "in all respects" after "correspond"
9	4	9	"androgens, etc. which made"	"androgens etc. These made"
9	4	14	"synthetically"	"exclusively by syntheses"
10	1	3	Insert after	"stage" "The investigation of sex hormones requires careful organisation and is beset with considerable experimental difficulties and so far as is known little progress has yet been made in India in this field"
10	3	4	Insert 'a' before	"nitrogenous"
11	2	1	...	Read the first line as "Anaemia is unfortunately very common in this country and liver and stomach extracts are widely used in India for the treatment not only of anaemia but also of"